

acid from the seeds²⁻⁴ and two flavonal glycosides⁵ astragalín (kaempferol-3-glucoside) and nicotiflorín (kaempferol-3-rhamnoglucoside) from its leaves and nycthanthíc acid from the heartwood of this plant were earlier reported. Our results on the reinvestigation of its leaves are presented in this note.

The leaf powder (1 kg) was successively extracted with n-hexane, ethylacetate and methanol. The wax free hexane extract on chromatography on neutral alumina⁶ yielded nycthanthíc acid (80 mg), m.p. 223-5°, [α]_D+81.5°, M⁺ 440, methyl ester, m.p. 125° and friedelin (75 mg), m.p. 255°, oxime, colourless plates m.p. 292-4°. The identity was established by comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the respective authentic specimens.

The detanned ethylacetate extract, on concentration left mannitol, m.p. 166°, hexaacetate, 125-6° and hexabenzooate, 149° and the residue on column chromatography on silica gel yielded β -sitosterol (100 mg), m.p. 135° and two more triterpenes, lupeol, m.p. 210° (50 mg) and oleanolic acid (125 mg) m.p. 310°, [α]_D+78° which were identified by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the appropriate authentic samples.

Present reinvestigation of the leaves of *N. arbor-tristis* reveals the presence of friedelin, lupeol and oleanolic acid in addition to nycthanthíc acid, the only triterpene reported by earlier workers. Further, the co-occurrence of oleanolic acid with the corresponding 3-4 seco acid, nycthanthíc acid is of biogenetic significance.

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Chemical Investigation of *Grewia populifolia* Vahl and *Phaulopsis parviflora* Willd*

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GREWIA *populifolia* Vahl [Syn: *Grewia tanax* (Forsk) Aschers], is a medicinally important plant of the family *Tilliaceae*¹. It is a much branched shrub found in Punjab, Sind, Rajputana and Western India, down to the Nilgiri Hills. Mucilage of the bark of *G. populifolia* is reported to have bactericidal activity and also to be used in the treatment of tuberculosis in hilly areas. Some work on

seeds², stem³ and stem bark⁴ of this plant has been reported. Results of chemical examination of the leaves of this plant, on which no phytochemical work has been done so far are reported here.

Phaulopsis parviflora Willd [syn: *Phaulopsis dorsiflora* (Retz) Santapau] is a prostrate closely branched perennial herb belonging to the family *Acanthaceae* occurring throughout India excepting north-western region⁵. Only the leaves of this plant has been investigated earlier⁶. A systematic chemical investigation of the whole plant was, therefore, undertaken and the results are reported.

G. populifolia: The air dried powdered leaves of *G. populifolia* were exhaustively extracted in turn with petroleum ether (60-80°), benzene and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether (60-80°) extract was subjected to chromatographic analysis over silica gel. The petroleum ether (60-80°) eluate furnished a solid, m.p. 85-87°; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3325, 1450, 1375, 1060, 720 and 718 cm⁻¹. It did not respond to Leibermann-Burchardt test for sterols and triterpenes and was identified as triacontanol by usual comparison (m.m.p; co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample.

Elution of the column with petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (3:1) mixture afforded a solid which on crystallisation from petroleum ether (40-60°) furnished colourless granules, m.p. 82-83° and analysed for C₃₄H₆₈O₂ (M⁺, 508). It did not respond to Leibermann-Burchardt test for sterols and triterpenes nor did it give any colouration with tetranitromethane. The compound in its ir spectrum exhibited absorption peaks at 3320 (OH), 1710 (Carbonyl), 1460, 1370, 725, 715 (aliphatic long chain) and 1066 cm⁻¹ (C-O stretching of secondary hydroxyl group) and formed an amorphous acetate, $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1720 cm⁻¹, on acetylation with acetic anhydride-pyridine, and a diol, m.p. 71-73°; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3300 cm⁻¹ on reduction with LiAlH₄ in THF.

The nmr spectrum (90MHz, CDCl₃) of the compound recorded signals at δ .90, 6H (2CH₃), 1.25, 52H (26CH₂), 1.75, 4H (2 CH₂, β to >C=O), 2.30, 4H (2CH₂, α to >C=O and around 4.00, 1H (-CHOH) indicating it to be a straight chain saturated aliphatic hydroxy ketone.

Further elaboration of the structure of this hydroxyketone has been possible from the mass spectral study. The mass spectrum of the compound recorded peak at m/e 509 (M+1) as expected for unsymmetrical ketones⁷. The other significant ion peaks appeared at m/e 353 (α -fission to carbonyl group), 183 (α -fission to carbonyl), 368 (McLafferty), 213 (α -fission to hydroxyl group), 198 (McLafferty) and 325 (α -fission to hydroxyl group).

All the above data conclusively show that the compound is tetratriacont-21-ol-12-one (I) and appears to be a new one

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Further elution of the column with benzene afforded β -sitosterol, m.p. 135-36°, acetate m.p. 127-28°, identical (m.m.p. and co-tlc) with authentic sample.

Benzene extract of the defatted plant on usual chromatographic resolution over silica gel furnished triacontanol and β -sitosterol, while chloroform extract on chromatographic resolution yielded only triacontanol.

P. parviflora: The air dried powdered whole plant of *P. parviflora* was extracted successively with petroleum ether (60-80°), benzene and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether (60-80°) extract was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (60-80°) benzene (1:1) mixture gave a solid crystallisable from methanol in shining white flakes, m.p. 135-36°. It responded positive in Leibermann-Burchardt test and was characterised as β -sitosterol by m.m.p. and co-ir with authentic sample. Further elution of the column with the same solvent yielded another sterol crystallised from chloroform-methanol (1:1) mixture, m.p. 145-46°; acetate m.p. 144°, identified as γ -sitosterol from m.m.p. co-tlc and co-ir with authentic specimen. The concentrated benzene and chloroform extract of the plant on chromatography over alumina yielded only β -sitosterol.

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Chemical Investigation of *Alysicarpus longifolius* Leaves

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*ALYSICARPUS longifolius*¹ Wright and Arn (Leguminosae), an annual herb commonly grows throughout the tropical region. The plant is reputed

for its medicinal values² and potential use as a forage. Literature revealed that no work, has been reported on the chemistry of this plant. Isolation and identification of myricyl alcohol, β -sitosterol, β -sitosterol acetate, rutin, pinitol along with an aliphatic ester and a flavonol are reported here. The latter two are being investigated further. The identity of the compounds was established on the basis of m.m.p. co-tlc, uv, ir, mass and comparison with authentic samples.

Experimental

The leaves were collected locally during July and August and contained crude protein 20.7, calcium 2.24 and phosphorus 0.29%. Powdered air-dried leaves (1 kg) were exhaustively extracted with ethanol (95%) under reflux. The alcoholic extract on concentration and cooling deposited a yellow crystalline compound (B). The remaining extract was successively fractionated into petroleum ether, benzene, ethyl-acetate and butanol fractions.

Petroleum ether fraction: It was chromatographed on silica gel column. Elution with different solvents and their mixtures yielded the following compounds. Compound A, (Petroleum ether-benzene 8:2). On crystallisation from acetone a white crystalline product m.p. 74°, MS (m/e M⁺ 732) was obtained showing strong ir absorption at 1740 and 1175 cm⁻¹ suggestive of an aliphatic ester. Myricyl alcohol³; m.p. and mm.p. with an authentic sample, 86-87°, acetate, m.p. 70-71°; β -sitosterol^{3,4}-m.p. 136-137°, (α)_D -33°; acetate, m.p. 129°; β -sitosterol acetate, m.p. 129°.

Ethyl acetate fraction: Rutin m.p. 186-187°, identical (m.p. and ir) with an authentic sample.

Butanol fraction: Pinitol m.p. 186°, identical (ms and ir) with an authentic specimen, penta-acetate, m.p. 98°.

Compound B, was obtained from alcohol as yellow crystals m.p. 197°, gave positive Shinoda Test⁴⁻⁵ (Mg+HCl) for flavonol, uv

λ (MeOH)_{max} 272, 335, nm : λ (MeOH+AlCl₃)_{max} 279, 352, nm :

λ (MeOH+AlCl₃+HCl)_{max} 291, 352 nm : λ (MeOH+NaOMe)_{max} 277,

362 nm. There was no shift on addition of sodium acetate. The ir spectrum exhibited characteristic peaks at ν _{max}^{KBr} 3400, 2920, 1645, 1590, 1550, 1485 and 1445 ;

acetate (acetic anhydride+pyridine) crystallized from methanol as colourless silky needles m.p. 179°.

IR ν _{max}^{KBr} 1740 cm⁻¹, ms (m/e M⁺ 656).

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